

Conference Abstract

Acetylenotrophic and Diazotrophic *Bradyrhizobium* sp. Strain I71 from Trichloroethylene-Contaminated Soils

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Abstract

Acetylene (C₂H₂) is a trace constituent of Earth's modern atmosphere and is used by acetylenotrophic microorganisms as their sole carbon and energy source (Akob et al. 2018). Acetylenotrophs hydrate acetylene through a reaction catalyzed by acetylene hydratase, which is a heterogeneous class of enzymes. As of 2018, there were 15 known strains of acetylenotrophs including aerobic species affiliated with the Actinobacteria, and Firmicutes and anaerobic species affiliated with the Desulfobacterota. However, we hypothesized that there was an unknown diversity of acetylenotrophs in nature. We recently expanded the known distribution of acetylenotrophs via the isolation of the aerobic acetylenotroph, *Bradyrhizobium* sp. strain I71, from trichloroethylene (TCE)-contaminated soils (Akob et al. 2022). Strain I71 is a member of the class Alphaproteobacteria, and this is the first

observation of an aerobic acetylenotroph in the Proteobacteria phylum. The isolate grows via heterotrophic and acetylenotrophic metabolism, and is diazotrophic, capable of nitrogen fixation. Acetylenotrophy and nitrogen fixation are the only two enzymatic reactions known to transform acetylene, and this is only the second isolate known to carry out both reactions (Akob et al. 2017, Baesman et al. 2019). Members of *Bradyrhizobium* are well studied for their abilities to improve plant health and increase crop yields by providing bioavailable nitrogen. The unique capability of *Bradyrhizobium* sp. strain I71 to utilize acetylene may increase the genus' economic impact beyond agriculture as acetylenotrophy is closely linked to bioremediation of chlorinated contaminants (Mao et al. 2017, Gushgari-Doyle et al. 2021). Based on genome, cultivation, and protein prediction analysis, the ability to consume acetylene is likely not widespread within the genus *Bradyrhizobium*. These findings suggest that the suite of phenotypic capabilities of strain I71 may be unique and make it a good candidate for further study in several research avenues such as contaminant biodegradation and nutrient cycling.

Keywords

microbial ecology, contaminants, environmental health, acetylene, nitrogen fixation, chlorinated solvents

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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